

ECONOMICS OF ONION SEED PRODUCTION IN WASHIM DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present study has been conducted to examine the "Production And Marketing Of Onion Seed In Washim District". The study was carried out through collection of data by interview method. The primary data was collected from 120 Onion seed grower. Three Tahsil were selected on the basis of availability of data, i.e. Washim, Risod and Malegaon were selected for present investigation and two villages are selected from each tahasil, and from each village 20 growers of onion seed were selected to form a sample of 120 growers. The data pertains for year 2024-25. The highest per hectare cost of cultivation (Cost C₃) was observed among small-size farms, whereas the medium-size group achieved the highest benefit-cost ratio (1.66). In estimation of cost of cultivation, seedling, rental value of land, hired labour and machinery charges were the major cost items.

Keyword: cost of cultivation, onion seed, benefit cost ratio

Introduction

In Washim district of Maharashtra, the cultivated area for onion seed is relatively small compared to other crops due to the predominance of unirrigated land. Despite this, onion remains an extensively cultivated crop, leading to a high annual demand for fresh seeds. Seed plays a crucial role in productive agriculture, acting as a catalyst that enhances the effectiveness of other inputs such as fertilizers, water, and pesticides. Without high-quality seeds, investments in these inputs yield suboptimal results, making seed one of the most vital components in agriculture. Since onion seeds have limited viability, annual production is essential to meet demand. The Green Revolution's success largely stemmed from the availability of high-yielding seed varieties. Improved varieties and hybrids with high genetic purity, superior germination rates, minimal impurities, and disease resistance have significantly transformed Indian

agriculture. However, onion bulb production per unit area remains low. In Maharashtra, the annual demand for onion seeds is around 600 tons, while systematic production is only 300 tons, indicating a considerable gap between supply and demand. Onion seed production follows a biennial cycle, primarily utilizing the bulb-to-seed method, which allows growers to eliminate undesirable or diseased bulbs.

Methodology

The study was conducted in the Washim district of Maharashtra state for the year 2024-25. The three tehsils from Washim district has been selected. Similarly, two villages from each tehsils and 20 farmers from each village was selected for present study. As such total 120 farmers was selected purposively. To calculate the cost and returns of Onion seed simple tabular analysis followed by standard cost concept

Result and discussion**Table 1. Cost and return of onion seed growers in small farmers. (Rs/ha)**

Sr. No.	Items	Unit	Quantity	Rs./Unit	Total Cost	Per cent to Cost "C3"
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Labour					
	Male	Days	45.16	294.45	13297.46	4.47
	Female	Days	94.26	229.28	21611.60	7.26
	Sub Total		139.42		34909.06	11.73
2	Bullock Labour	(Pair days)	8.70	878.49	7642.84	2.57
3	Machine labour	Hours	13.20	978.26	12913.01	4.34
4	Seedling	Kg.	30.23	3000.39	90701.75	30.46
5	Manures	Qtls.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	Fertilizer					
	N	Kg	102.37	28.94	2962.59	1.00
	P	Kg	55.72	34.10	1900.00	0.64
	K	Kg	36.75	44.34	1629.50	0.55
	Sub Total				6492.08	2.18
7	Irrigation charges	Rs.	0.00	0.00	3810.53	1.28
9	Insecticide (Plant Protection)	Rs.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Incidental charges	Rs.			565.26	0.19
11	Repairing Charges	Rs.			282.63	0.09
14	Plant Protection	Rs.			2788.89	0.94
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	Rs.			160106.05	53.77
16	Interest on working Capital				3202.12	1.08
17	Depreciation	Rs.			7313.81	2.46
18	Land Revenue	Rs.			45.00	0.02
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)			-	170666.98	57.32
20	Rental Value of leased Land	Rs.		-	-	-
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)			-	170666.98	57.32
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%	Rs.			12280.81	4.12
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)				182947.79	61.45

21	Rental Value of owned Land	Rs.			78568.55	26.39
22	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)				261516.34	87.83
23	Family Labour					
	Male	Days	20.64	292.75	6042.40	2.03
	Female	Days	13.51	230.33	3111.70	1.05
	Sub Total	Days	34.15		9154.10	3.08
24	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)				192101.89	64.52
25	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)				270670.44	90.91
26	10% Cost C2*				27067.04	9.09
27	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)				297737.48	100.00
28	Value of main produce	Rs.	8.00	58960.16	471681.29	
29	Value of By-produce/ha.	Rs.	0.00	0.00	0.00	
30	Gross return				471681.29	
31	Per quintal cost of Production				37217.19	

(Figures in parentheses are indicate the percentages to the total cost c₃)

As reflected in the table 1, growers incurred an expenditure of ₹2,97,737.48 per hectare for onion seed production, categorized under Cost C₃. The primary components contributing to this expenditure were seedlings, imputed rental value of land, hired labour and machinery charges, which accounted for 30.46 per cent, 26.39 per cent, 11.72 per cent, and 4.34 per cent of the total cost, respectively. The average yield per hectare was estimated at 8.00 quintals with gross return of Rs. 471681.29 per hectare of onion seed production of small growers.

Table 2. Cost and return of onion seed grower in medium farmers. (Rs/ha)

SN	ITEMS	Unit	Quantity	Rs./Unit	Total cost	Per cent to Cost "C3"
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Human Labour					
	Male	Days	44.86	292.66	13128.65	4.59
	Female	Days	93.67	228.14	21369.56	7.48
	Sub total		138.53	249.03	34498.21	12.07
2	Bullock Labour	Pair	8.97	869.75	7801.67	2.73
3	Machine Labour	Hrs.	12.51	979.09	12248.45	4.29
4	Seedling	Qtls.	30.17	2960.16	89308.3	31.26
5	Manures	Qtls.	0	0	0	0.00
	Fertilizer					
6	N	Kg.	103.25	27.22	2810.46	0.98
	P	Kg.	48.31	35.33	1706.79	0.60
	K	Kg.	32.69	41.68	1362.51	0.48
	Sub Total				5843.76	2.06
7	Irrigation charges	Rs.	0	0	3814.22	1.33
9	Insecticide (Plant Protection)	Rs.	0	0	0	0.00
10	Incidental charges	Rs.			631.62	0.22
11	Repairing Charges	Rs.			315.81	0.11
14	Plant Protection	Rs.			2673.71	0.94
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	Rs.			157171.76	55.01
16	Interest on working Capital				3143.43	1.10
17	Depreciation	Rs.			4244.09	1.49
18	Land Revenue	Rs.			45	0.02
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)			0	164604.29	57.61
20	Rental Value of leased Land	Rs.		0	0.00	0.00
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)			0	164604.29	57.61
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%	Rs.			6960.63	2.44
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)				171564.92	60.04
24	Rental Value of owned Land	Rs.			79620.68	27.87
25	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)				251185.60	87.91
26	Family Human Labour					
	Male	Days	18.77	291.68	5474.9	1.92
	Female	Days	13.47	229.61	3092.88	1.08
	Sub Total	Days	32.24	265.75	8567.78	3.00

27	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)				180132.70	63.04
28	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)				259753.38	90.91
29	10% Cost C2*				25975.34	9.09
30	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)				285728.72	100.00
31	Value of main produce hectare	(Rs.)	7.99	59793.57	477994.07	
32	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Rs.)	0	0	0	
33	Gross return				477994.07	
34	Per quintal cost of Production				35742.57	

(Figures in parentheses are the percentages to the total cost c₃)

As reflected in the table 2, growers incurred an expenditure of ₹285728.72 per hectare for onion seed production, categorized under Cost C₃. The primary components contributing to this expenditure were seedlings, imputed rental value of land, hired labour and machinery

charges, which accounted for 31.26 per cent, 27.87 per cent, 12.07 per cent, and 4.29 per cent of the total cost, respectively. The average yield per hectare was estimated at 7.99 quintals with gross return of 477994.07 per hectare of onion seed production in medium growers.

Table 3. Cost and return of onion seed growers in large farmers. (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	ITEMS	Unit	Quantity	Rs./Unit	Total Cost	Per cent to Cost "C3"
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Labour					
	Male	Days	45.06	295.89	13332.62	4.75
	Female	Days	89.69	229.16	20553.41	7.33
	Sub Total	Days	134.75		33886.03	12.08
2	Bullock Labour	Hrs	8.39	842.51	7068.64	2.52
3	Machine Labour	Hrs.	12.17	983.47	11968.78	4.27
4	Seedling	Qtls.	30.32	2961.31	89787.06	32.00
5	Manures	Qtls.	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	Fertilizer					
	N	Kg.	93.61	25.76	2411.39	0.86
	P	Kg.	49.1	31.65	1554.02	0.55
	K	Kg.	27.59	42.58	1174.78	0.42
	Sub Total				5140.19	1.83
7	Irrigation charges	Rs.	0	0.00	3937.47	1.40
9	Insecticide (Plant Protection)	Rs.	0	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Incidental charges	Rs.			547.86	0.20
11	Repairing Charges	Rs.			273.93	0.10
14	Plant Protection	Rs.			2341.79	0.83
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	Rs.			154951.75	55.23
16	Interest on working Capital				3099.04	1.10
17	Depreciation	Rs.			6730.69	2.40
18	Land Revenue	Rs.			45.00	0.02
19	COST "A1" (Items 15 to 18)			313039.61	164826.48	58.75
20	Rental Value of leased Land	Rs.		0.00	0.00	0.00
21	COST "A2" (Item 19 to 20)			170418.56	164826.48	58.75
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%	Rs.			6184.12	2.20
23	COST "B1" (Items 19 + 22)				171010.60	60.95
24	Rental Value of owned Land	Rs.			77886.29	27.76
25	COST "B2" (Items 23 + 24)				248896.89	88.71
26	Family Labour					
	Male	Days	13.31	293.30	3903.78	1.39
	Female	Days	10.05	225.56	2266.87	0.81
	Sub Total	Days	23.36		6170.65	2.20
27	COST "C1"(Item 23+26)				177181.25	63.15
28	COST "C2"(Item 25+26)				255067.54	90.91
29	10% Cost C2*				25506.75	9.09
30	COST "C3"(Item 30+31)				280574.29	100.00
31	Value of main produce	(Rs.)	7.84	59675.66	467587.77	
32	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Rs.)	0	0.00	0.00	
33	Gross return				467587.76	
34	Per quintal cost of Production				35808.15	

(Figures in parentheses are indicate the percentages to the total cost c₃)

As reflected in the table 3, growers incurred an expenditure of ₹280574.29 per hectare for onion seed production, categorized under Cost C₃. The primary components contributing to this expenditure were seedlings, imputed rental value of land, hired labour and machinery

charges, which accounted for 32.00 per cent, 27.76 per cent, 12.08 per cent, and 4.27 per cent of the total cost, respectively. The average yield per hectare was estimated at 7.84 quintals with gross return of Rs. 467587.77 per hectare of onion seed production of large growers.

Table 4. Cost and return of onion seed growers in overall farmers. (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	ITEMS	Unit	Quantity	Rs./Unit	Total	Per cent to Cost "C3"
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	Hired Labour					
	Male	Days	45.16	294.45	13297.46	4.65
	Female	Days	94.26	229.28	21611.60	7.56
	Total		139.42		34909.06	12.20
2	Bullock Labour	Hrs	8.11	913.99	7412.43	2.59
3	Machine charges	Hrs	12.55	975.29	12239.83	4.28
4	Seedling	Qtls	30.26	2968.60	89829.83	31.40
5	Manures	Qtls	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
6	Fertilizer					
	N	Kg	98.39	28.23	2777.55	0.97
	P	Kg	50.23	35.81	1798.74	0.63
	K	Kg	31.05	44.12	1369.93	0.48
	Sub Total		179.67		5946.21	2.08
7	Irrigation charges	Rs.	0.00	0.00	3873.37	1.35
9	Insecticide (Plant Protection)	Rs.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
10	Incidental charges	Rs.			577.15	0.20
11	Repairing Charges	Rs.			288.58	0.10
14	Plant Protection	Rs.			2536.64	0.89
15	Working Capital (1 to 14)	Rs.			157613.10	55.10
16	Interest on working Capital				3152.26	1.10
17	Depreciation	Rs.			6089.04	2.13
18	Land Revenue	Rs.			45.00	0.02
19	COST "A ₁ " (Items 15 to 18)			0.00	166899.40	58.35
20	Rental Value of leased Land	Rs.		-	-	-
21	COST "A ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)			0.00	166899.40	58.35
22	Int. on Fix.Cap. @ 10%	Rs.			7685.82	2.69
23	COST "B ₁ " (Items 19 + 22)				174585.22	61.04
21	Rental Value of owned Land	Rs.			78023.82	27.28
22	COST "B ₂ " (Items 23 + 24)				252609.04	88.31
23	Family Labour					0.00
	Male	Days	16.27	292.68	4761.90	1.66
	Female	Days	11.67	228.34	2664.72	0.93
	Sub Total	Days	27.94		7426.62	2.60
24	COST "C ₁ "(Item 23+26)				182011.84	63.63
25	COST "C ₂ "(Item 25+26)				260035.66	90.91
26	10% Cost C ₂ *				26003.57	9.09
27	COST "C ₃ "(Item 30+31)				286039.23	100.00
28	Vaue main produce	Rs.	7.92	59143.04	468412.90	
29	Value of By-produce/ha.	Rs.	0.00	0.00	0.00	
30	Gross return				468412.69	
31	Per quintal cost of Production				36116.06	

(Figures in parentheses are indicate the percentages to the total cost c₃)

As reflected in the table 4, growers incurred an expenditure of ₹280574.29 per hectare for onion seed production, categorized under Cost C₃. The primary components contributing to this expenditure were seedlings, imputed rental value of land, hired labour and machinery

charges, which accounted for 31.40 per cent, 27.28 per cent, 12.20 per cent, and 4.28 per cent of the total cost, respectively. The average yield per hectare was estimated at 7.92 quintals. With gross return of Rs. 286039.23 per hectare in overall onion growers in onion seed production.

Table 5. Economics of onion seed production. (Value in Rs/ha)

Sr No.	Particulars	Small group	Medium group	Large group	Overall group
1	Grass Returns	471681.29	477994.07	467587.76	468412.69
2	Cost of cultivation at				
a	Cost "A ₁ "	170666.98	164604.29	164826.48	166899.40

b	Cost"A ₂ "	170666.98	164604.29	164826.48	166899.40
c	Cost"B ₁ "	182947.79	171564.92	171010.60	174585.22
d	Cost"B ₂ "	261516.34	251185.60	248896.89	252609.04
e	Cost"C ₁ "	192101.89	180132.70	177181.25	182011.84
f	Cost"C ₂ "	270670.44	259753.38	255067.54	260035.66
g	Cost"C ₃ "	297737.48	285728.72	280574.29	286039.23
3	Net Return Over				
a	Cost"A ₁ "	301014.31	313389.78	302761.28	301513.29
b	Cost"A ₂ "	301014.31	313389.78	302761.28	301513.29
c	Cost"B ₁ "	288733.50	306429.15	296577.16	293827.47
d	Cost"B ₂ "	210164.95	226808.47	218690.87	215803.65
e	Cost"C ₁ "	279579.40	297861.37	290406.51	286400.85
f	Cost"C ₂ "	201010.85	218240.69	212520.22	208377.03
g	Cost"C ₃ "	173943.81	192265.35	187013.47	182373.46
4	Benefit - Cost Ratio at				
a	Cost"A ₁ "	2.76	2.90	2.84	2.81
b	Cost"A ₂ "	2.76	2.90	2.84	2.81
c	Cost"B ₁ "	2.58	2.79	2.73	2.68
d	Cost"B ₂ "	1.80	1.90	1.88	1.85
e	Cost"C ₁ "	2.46	2.65	2.64	2.57
f	Cost"C ₂ "	1.74	1.84	1.83	1.80
g	Cost"C ₃ "	1.58	1.67	1.66	1.64

As reflected in Table 5 the gross return is highest in medium growers with Rs. 477994.07 per hectare followed by small and large growers with Rs. 471681.29 and Rs. 467587.76 per hectare, respectively. At overall level the gross return was Rs. 468412.69. Similarly, the cost of cultivation of is highest in small growers with Rs. 297737 per hectare followed by medium and large growers with Rs. 285728.72 and Rs. 280574.29 per hectare, respectively. At overall level the cost of cultivation was Rs.286039.23. The Net Return of onion seed production was highest in medium farmer with Rs. 192265.35 followed by large and small growers with Rs. 182373.46 and Rs. 173943.81 per hectare. At overall level the net return of onion seed production was Rs. 182373.46 per hectare. The benefit-cost ratio was highest in medium growers with 1.67 followed by large and small growers with 1.66 and 1.58 per hectare, respectively. At overall level the benefit-cost ratio was 1.64 per hectare.

Conclusion

Per hectare Cost 'A₁' was highest in small size group i.e. 170666.98 followed by large size and medium size group i.e. 164826.48 and 164604.29 and overall Cost 'A₁' observed 166899.40 respectively. The

per hectare total cost of cultivation of onion seed i.e. Cost 'C₃' was highest in small size group i.e. 297737.48 and followed by medium and large size group i.e. 285728.72 and 280574.29 respectively. Overall Cost 'C₃' was observed was 286039.23. The benefit cost ratio of onion seed cultivation at Cost 'C₃' was highest in medium size group followed by large and small group i.e. 1.66 and 1.58. Overall benefit cost ratio was observed 1.64.

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